

UNDERSTANDING THE PERCEPTION OF CONSUMERS' REGARDING OBSTACLES ON DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUPI AND DAKSHINA KANNADA REGION

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ABSTRACT

Today consumer behaviour has become the central topic of marketing because consumer is the king of the marketing. As everywhere technological changes are taking place in the modern world, there is a change/advancement even in method of payment. But consumers should be aware about this advancement in method of payment because if lack of awareness then it leads the consumer to hesitate/resist digital payment system. So there is a need of consumer education on digital services which supports the adoption of digital modes of payments. This paper makes an attempt to understand the consumers' perception and behaviour towards digital payment services and also tries to identify the causes of user's resistance. This research paper focuses on the perception and attitude of consumers of Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region regarding obstacles on digital payment system. The data is collected both from primary and secondary sources. Around 1,000 samples were taken in Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region for this survey. The variables that influence the consumer's to adopt to electronic payments services are identified to analyze the impact of digital payments.

Keywords: Digital payments, consumers, demonetization, consumers' education, digital security.

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for improving the trends of digital payments system is very important to make a transparency in all the transactions. In India to promote the digital payment system, Government started a campaign called the Digital India. As part of promoting cashless business and converting India into less-cash culture, various modes of digital payments are made available like internet banking, mobile wallets, banking card, USSD, UPI, AEPS, banks pre-paid cards, point of sale, mobile banking, micro ATMs, etc. Digital payment system is completely based on the modern technology which includes electronic means and internet. So the marketers need to understand and cater for a wide variety of consumers' segments. Time and experience is needed for customers to adjust to new types of risks associated with digital payment. Due to unawareness, lack of education, lack of trust (fear on security for their money), perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, the consumers are resistant to adopt digital payment services most the time. So it is necessary to arrange some programmes on digital payment system to educate the consumers.

2. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To understand the Perception of consumers' regarding obstacles on digital payments.
- 2) To study the difficulties faced by consumers in using digital services.
- 3) To analyse the reasons behind the problems faced by the consumers.
- 4) To identify the solutions for the problem faced.

3. METHODOLOGY

The resources collected to prepare this paper were both from primary and secondary data.

PRIMARY DATA

Primary data were collected through survey by distributing questionnaires to 100 students of various colleges in Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region. Simple percentage analysis has been done to evaluate the data.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data collected with the help of various books, newspapers, journals, internet and some online thesis and magazines etc.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this questionnaire is to find out the opinion of few consumers' of Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region about digital payment system.

4.1 Do you have knowledge on Digital Payment System?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	450	45%
No	550	55%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 consumers only 450 respondents were having knowledge on Digital Payment System.

4.2 How do you get to know the knowledge about Digital Payment System?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Through Friends	100	10%
Social Media	420	42%
Through Advertisements	100	10%
Through Bank	380	38%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents only 380 consumers got the awareness about Digital Payment system from Bank.

4.3 How many times have you done digital transaction before?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Only Once	200	20%
Two	250	25%
Three	250	25%
More than Four	300	30%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents an around 20% of consumers have not used digital payment system much.

4.4 What is your perception towards digital payment system?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Trustworthy	520	52%
Untrustworthy	480	48%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents 48% of consumers are still worried about digital payment system.

4.5 Level of agreement to the following questions.

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I think Digital Payment System is Risky.	500	160	040	150	150
Digital Payment System is difficult.	400	080	230	180	110
I prefer to withdraw money from bank	500	040	150	120	190
Digital Payment System is safe.	150	150	150	200	350
I think digital payment is better substitute for traditional cash payment system	380	180	130	110	200
Digital Payment is cost saving	300	100	320	150	130
Digital Payment is not time consuming	300	070	100	220	310
More guidance from the educational institutions, banks and Government regarding this is required.	480	280	40	130	070

Interpretation:

- ▶ Around 50% of consumers agree that digital payment system is risky.
- ▶ 40% of consumers feel that digital payment system is difficult.
- ▶ 50% of consumers strongly like to withdraw the money from bank.
- ▶ Only 15% of consumers are stated that digital payment system is safe.
- ▶ Around 38% of consumers think that online banking is better substitute for traditional banking system.
- ▶ 30% of consumers have strongly stated that digital payment is not costly.
- ▶ 30% of consumers strongly believe that digital payment system saves the time.
- ▶ 38% of consumers are strongly agreed that more participation of education institutions, banks regarding encouragement, support, motivation, and in giving information about digital payment is required.

5. FINDINGS

- 1) Out of 1000 consumers only 450 consumers were thought about digital payment system Remaining 550 consumers are not interested in that.
- 2) Out of 1000 respondents only 380 consumers got the awareness about digital payment system from the bank. Through friends 100 consumers, through advertisements 100. But majority of the consumers responded that they got the information about the digital payment system from social media.
- 3) Out of 1000, 300 consumers have used more than four times digital transaction before.
- 4) 500 consumers strongly agree that digital payment system is risky. 160 customers support to this statement. Whereas 40 consumers are in dilemma. 300 customers are disagreeing with this.
- 5) 400 consumers strongly feel that digital payment system is difficult. 80 consumers support for this. 230 consumers are there in both the sides. Whereas 390 consumers feel that digital payment system is not difficult.
- 6) Out of 1000 respondents 50% of consumers like to make cash payment. It clearly indicates that still they feel comfortable with traditional banking system.
- 7) 30% of consumers realised that digital payment system saves the time. It means for rest of them still awareness is required.
- 8) 48% of respondents strongly say that they need guidance from educational institutions and banks regarding digital payment system. It means they are interested to learn new system.

6. SUGGESTIONS

The need for improving the trends of digital payments system in India is very important. But changing consumer behavior takes many years. From the finding it clearly indicates that still most of the consumers want traditional method of payment because of unawareness, lack of education, perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, the consumers are resistant to adopt digital payment services. And moreover they are scared enough to use digital payment system this is because of lack of trust (fear on security for their money). Managing information security is a very complex issue. But the future of digital payment system is secure due to increasing adoption and arrival of new technologies to address existing limitations. So the banks must educate people about net banking services provided by their respective banks to their customer while opening the account. For that banks should identify reasons for resistance and guide them properly by proper marketing campaigns, communication with customers, customer training, providing user friendly website design and the banks must make their customers feel safer by providing more security other than OTP. Government should provide necessary infrastructure facilities for the effective implementation of digital payments plans. As digital payment methods are based on cards, mobile apps and internet and it needs technical knowledge, even Government needs to arrange more awareness programs to make the people to know the terms related to digital India. It is found through the study that only some of the consumers go for digital payment. So trainings programs must be taken up in schools, colleges and Universities, Conferences, Seminar and workshops are required to be organized to discuss and create awareness about the various payments methods and new technologies and the benefits of digital payment services among customers.

7. LIMITATIONS

The sample size for this study is based on the availability of respondents in the target group, which could be a limitation in generalizing the result of findings. Therefore, a similar empirical finding with a wider sample size will be necessary in order to determine the generalised conclusion about rural people participation.

8. CONCLUSION

The most recent technological advancement is the evolution of Digital Payment System. Slowly India is moving from cash to less-cash economy. But still it has not been accepted by all the customers. The reasons may be lack of trust, lack of technical knowledge, fear of traceability of transaction, habit, unawareness, lack of education, perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, etc. It is found through the study that only some of the customers use digital payment system. So Youth centered trainings programs must be taken up in schools, colleges and Universities, Conferences, Seminar and workshops are required to be organized to discuss and create awareness about the various payments methods and new technologies among customers by the Government, education institutions, and banks. If awareness is created on customers towards digital payment system so that they will encourage the future generation too.

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10. DECLARATION

We do here by declare that it is the original work, and the paper has neither been published/presented nor sent for publication anywhere else.

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